

THE IMPACT OF A STEM PARTNERSHIP ON TRANSFORMATIVE TEACHING AND LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

As educators committed to a transformative teaching and learning we need to actively engage with our new generation, promote critical thinking, and share knowledge and skills to promote sustainable developments in order to build that much needed Science Capital. At this moment the UK engineering industry is experiencing two main issues: i) a shortfall of 20,000 graduate engineers per year and ii) lack of female engineers. These two issues are a key challenge that must be addressed to guarantee a sustainable economy. To pursue these goals a STEM partnership between Glasgow Caledonian University (GCU), the Royal Navy and six Primary Schools was funded by the Royal Society Partnership Grants scheme. In this project GCU's students worked collaboratively with 250 primary pupils from age 8 to 11 on the design and manufacturing of a Luge start ramp. Different workshops related to design, manufacturing, mechanical properties, welding and beyond were delivered by the STEM partners, while the pupils provided ideas to enhance the ramp's design and teachers reinforced the topics prior and after each workshop. The

project enables the evaluation of aspects related to the impact of actively involving young pupils in an engineering real life problem, making them act as engineers, and their change in perception towards Engineering. Other aspects that will be analysed are the impact of positive role models not only on the pupils but on pupils' influencers (teachers and parents), as well as the inclusivity and diversity as part of the commitment to a transformative education.

1 INTRODUCTION

The UK engineering industry is facing a shortfall of 20,000 graduate engineers per year and lack of female engineers, issues that must be addressed to guarantee a sustainable economy [1-3]. However, to achieve a sustainable economy it is essential to invest in education in order to develop Human Capital in general [4] and more specific Scientific and Technical Human Capital (STHC) [5]; this is clear from the UN Sustainable Development Goals, outcome 4.7 which states that all learners should receive education to develop their knowledge and skills to promote sustainable developments [6]. On the other hand previous research has highlighted that the development of science capital should start at primary levels where sustainable approaches to primary science education are essential [7-8], together with the importance to develop meta-skills that include problem-solving, critical thinking, communication, creativity and leadership in order to thrive in the 21st century fast changing environment at economic and social levels [8], and all this is possible through a Transformative Education [9-10].

2 RATIONALE

One of the factors that aggravates skills shortage in engineering is the lack of role models [11] specially in deprived areas where the lack of facilities, lack of resources and lack of opportunities are amplified [12]. In order to stimulate and inspire new generation in the areas of Science Technology, Engineering and Maths (STEM) it is key to engage them with positive role models specially in underrepresented sectors where they are less likely to choose STEM subjects [13-16].

Glasgow Caledonian University have been ranked amongst the top 50 universities in the world for social impact and top 12 for gender equality and reducing inequalities [17]. As part of the commitment to the community and to increase the amount of girls in our engineering programmes our students are provided with the opportunity to be involved in different public engagement events, to not only introduce to the community the different aspects involved in engineering, but to act as role models to inspire the new generation. The opportunity to be involved in a collaborative project together with primary pupils will benefit university students and primary pupils by allowing them to develop meta-skills through the participation and engagement in a real life engineering problem-solving activity with the help and support of all the STEM partners.

3 METHODOLOGY

A STEM partnership between Glasgow Caledonian University (GCU), the Royal Navy and six Primary Schools from varied demographic and SIMD (Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation) was funded by the Royal Society Partnership Grants scheme.

[18]. The Project entitled *The Olympic GB Luge team need a Luge starting ramp! Can pupils across Renfrewshire create the perfect design?*

The project entailed four GCU MEng mechanical engineering students being matched with 250 pupils from P4-P6 (ages 8-11) to Design and Manufacture the Luge Starting Ramp requested by the Royal Navy Luge Team .

The activity took place over a period of 10 months. Table 1 shows the activities led by each STEM partner involved.

Table 1. Activity delivered by the STEM partners involved and purpose

Partner	Activity	Purpose
GCU MEng Students	Workshops related to design, materials selection, material properties and welding.	Provide an understanding on factors that engineers need to consider during the design process with the aim that pupils could contribute on the enhancement of the ramp's design
Royal Navy Luge Team	Workshop related to Luge Sport and Winter Olympics	Awareness of Luge Sport and Winter Olympics. Development of competition skills
Royal Navy STEM Team	STEM workshops	Awareness of different types of engineering. Hands on activities in electrical circuits, coding, pneumatics, application of technology in submarines etc.
Teachers	Introduction and reinforcements	Optimal angle of the track to increase speed, effect of friction, testing materials, etc

The project was divided in 6 main stages as observed in Table 2

Table 2. Stages of the project

Stage	Description
1	Delivery of questionnaires to pupils, parents and teachers- before the project
2	Introduction of STEM partners to Primary Pupils- roles
3	Development of pupil's understanding in different topic-workshops- setting up challenges
4	Handover of the ramp- Visit to University-showcase the labs/workshops for the manufacturing of the ramp
5	Delivery of questionnaires to pupils, parents and teachers- after the project
6	Comparison and analysis of outcomes from questionnaires

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The STEM partnership provided the opportunity to bring positive role models to schools pupils, teachers and parents as part of a transformative education to build on meta-skills. The developed activities allowed pupils to work collaboratively, exchange knowledge, increase communication skills and apply critical thinking as part of the skills required for future career path ways, while observing further education at primary levels. A brief description of the impact on each participant is provided below.

4.1 Impact on Pupils

The project has allowed learners to develop their STEM skills whilst making links to further education and STEM careers. This is in agreement with previous research [14-15]

Pupil's quote: *"I have loved working with GCU students and the Royal Navy. Designing the luge for Team GB and getting the chance to try welding has been very cool."*

4.2. Impact on Teachers

The project has increased teacher confidence in teaching STEM as they have worked alongside STEM professionals from Glasgow Caledonian University and the Royal Navy. This collaborative and mutually beneficial approach has increased teachers' knowledge and engagement in the engineering element of STEM.

Teacher's quote: *"Every pupil has thoroughly enjoyed all aspects of the learning they have experienced. The unique opportunity to work with GCU and the Royal Navy has given pupils an insight of what it might be like to study STEM and to work in a STEM career in the future. It has certainly created a buzz around STEM in the classroom."*

4.3. Impact on Parents

Parents have commented on the fact that their children have the exciting opportunity to engage with universities whilst in primary school. This has allowed us to explore and tackle perceptions around university and highlight that a career in engineering is accessible whilst pupil engagement and interest increases in that field.

Parent's quote: *"My child hasn't stopped talking about all the class lessons/experiments and visits from GCU and the Royal Navy. I know when he has completed a task on the Luge project because he can't stop talking about it when he gets home!"*

4.4. Impact on MEng students

Students have mentioned how rewarding and satisfying the experience has been to be seen as role models to underrepresented sectors in general and to be able to engage with them by learning to use a simplistic language to communicate engineering concepts and provide the necessary information to interact with a young audience while keeping them engaged in the topic.

MEng student's quote: *"The STEM outreach program has impacted me on both a professional and personal level. Being able to impact the lives of young children is an incredible opportunity, and one in which I am proud to say I have been involved in. On a professional level, I have loved being involved in the outreach program. The positive experience and impact of the partnership and program has motivated me to pursue similar routes of STEM outreach and is something that I will endeavour to be involved in as I start my next chapter in engineering, post-graduation"*.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORK

- The value in outreach work between schools and university/industry cannot be underestimated as it widens learner perspective on engineering, and cultural capital whilst demonstrating the impact learners can make upon society through STEM skills
- Collaborative STEM projects allow everyone involved to develop/enhance meta-skills which will support learners to thrive in any environment (Social/educational/professional).
- This is an ongoing project and surveys to assess the quantitative impact before and after the project concludes will be conducted.

6 REFERENCES

- [1] UK engineering Facing Skills Crisis: Where are the jobs? (2019)
<https://www.randstad.co.uk/career-advice/job-skills/uk-engineering-facing-skills-crisis-where-are-jobs/> [Access 11/02/2022]
- [2] Shell UK boss: My industry has a 'girl problem' and we've got to fix it. (2019):
<https://www.telegraph.co.uk/women/womens-business/9947001/Shell-UK-Engineering-has-a-girl-problem-and-weve-got-to-fix-it.html> [Access 11/02/2022]
- [3] Royal Academy of Engineering 2020-2025 strategy
<https://www.raeng.org.uk/about-us/what-we-do/our-strategy> [Access 12/02/2022]
- [4] Ozturk, Ilhan (2001). "The role of education in economic development: a theoretical perspective". *Journal of Rural Development and Administration*, Volume XXXIII, No. 1, Winter 2001, pp. 39-47
- [5] Elizabeth A. Corley, Barry Bozeman, Xuefan Zhang, and Chin-Chang Tsai. (2019). "The expanded scientific and technical human capital model: the addition of a cultural dimension". *J Technol Transf.* 44:681–699
- [6] Transforming our World: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development Web.
<https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org> [Access 14/03/2022]
- [7] Archer, L., Dawson, E., DeWitt, J., Seakins, A., & Wong, B. (2015). "Science capital": A conceptual, methodological, and empirical argument for extending bourdieusian notions of capital beyond the arts. *Journal of research in science teaching*, 52(7), 922-948
- [8] A Human Future. Skills Development Scotland.
<https://www.skillsdevelopmentscotland.co> [Access 22/03/2022]
- [9] GCU Strategy 2030. <https://strategy2030.gcu.ac.uk> [Access 15/03/2022]
- [10] Royal Society: A broad and balanced curriculum: <https://royalsociety.org/topics-policy/projects/vision/science-to-18/> [Access 28/04/2022]
- [11] Lack of engineering role models aggravates skills shortage, says IET (2018)
<https://eandt.theiet.org/content/articles/2018/12/lack-of-engineering-role-models-aggravating-skills-shortage-says-iet/> [Access 06/04/2022]
- [12] Sally Macintyre, Laura Macdonald, Anne Ellaway (2008). "Do poorer people have poorer access to local resources and facilities? The distribution of local resources by area deprivation in Glasgow, Scotland". *Social Science & Medicine* 67, 900–914
- [13] The least and most popular undergraduate courses in the UK (2018):
<https://www.timeshighereducation.com/student/news/least-and-most-popular-undergraduate-courses-uk> [Access 1/04/2022]

- [14] Higher Education Student Statistics: UK, 2016/2017-Qualifications achieved (2018): <https://www.hesa.ac.uk/news/11-01-2018/sfr247-higher-education-student-statistics/qualifications> [Access 1/04/2022]
- [15] Daniel Rose (2004). The Potential of Role-Model Education. <https://infed.org/mobi/the-potential-of-role-model-education/> [Access 29/03/2022]
- [16] Inspiring The New Generation: How to Encourage Young People into Engineering (2022). <https://www.pmtoday.co.uk/inspiring-the-next-generation-how-to-encourage-young-people-into-engineering/> [Access 29/03/2022]
- [17] Times Higher Education (2019). Impact Ranking 2019 by SDG: Gender Equality. https://www.timeshighereducation.com/rankings/impact/2019/gender-equality#!/page/0/length/25/sort_by/rank/sort_order/asc/cols/undefined [Access 115/03/2022]
- [18] Royal Society: Partnership Grant <https://royalsociety.org/grants-schemes-awards/grants/partnership-grants/> [Access 22/03/2022]